

Eco-Friendly Cutting Fluids Sustainability: Comparing Non-Edible Vegetable Oils with Fuzzy AHP in Machining Processes

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Abstract- Growing environmental concerns and stricter industry regulations have amplified the need for sustainable machining methods and eco-friendly cutting fluids. Traditional mineral oil-based lubricants pose significant environmental and health risks due to their non-biodegradable nature and toxic ingredients. This research presents a structured decision-making framework for selecting sustainable cutting fluids using the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP). Four options—Neem seed oil, Jatropha oil, Pongamia oil, and mineral oil — were evaluated based on four main criteria: biodegradability, health effects, tool life, and surface finish. The FAHP model was validated through sensitivity analysis and experimental testing during the turning of AISI 1045 steel. Results show Neem seed oil achieved the highest overall sustainability score, supported by its excellent tool life (0.18 mm wear) and surface roughness ($R_a = 0.46 \mu\text{m}$). The model's consistency ratio was below 0.1, confirming dependable decisions. This combined FAHP experimental approach offers a robust, reproducible framework for selecting sustainable fluids, aiding Indian machining industries in replacing mineral oils with biodegradable, non-toxic, and cost-effective alternatives.

Keywords: Fuzzy AHP; sustainable machining; cutting fluids; non-edible vegetable oils; biodegradability; decision-making; green manufacturing; neem oil.

I. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing plays a vital role in the industry, involving various machining techniques. During machining, heat is produced from friction between the tool and the workpiece, affecting both tool durability and surface quality. Cutting fluids are used to reduce friction, resulting in better surface finishes and longer tool life (Sharma et al., 2015; Rahim & Dorairaju, 2018; Gariani et al., 2018). Growing population, industrial growth, and stricter environmental regulations on contamination and pollution have increased the need for eco-friendly cutting fluids. The goal is to lessen the environmental impact of machining in manufacturing. Cutting fluids, which include liquids and gases, are applied to the tool and workpiece to assist cutting. Data from Volza shows that India is the world's top importer of cutting oil (<https://www.volza.com>).

Traditional cutting fluids, such as mineral oil emulsions in water, pose environmental risks due to

disposal challenges (Pereira et al., 2016). Additionally, exposure to these fluids can lead to health problems for operators, including skin irritation, pneumonitis, and hypersensitivity (Singh et al., 2021; Alves & Oliveira, 2006). They also create an environment conducive to bacterial growth, which can be hazardous to workers (Hoff, 2002; Sluhan, 1994). Conversely, cutting fluids with excellent lubricating properties can safeguard the health of both operators and the environment (Chen et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2020). Kumar et al. (2022) emphasise that sustainability in machining encompasses social, economic, environmental, and technological aspects. Eco-friendly cutting fluids are non-toxic and devoid of harmful chemicals such as ammonium borohydride (a type of amine), chlorine, and sulfur. Dubey et al. (2024) noted that fluids derived from renewable, biodegradable, and non-toxic materials significantly reduce hazardous waste.

Furthermore, Junior et al. (2025) highlighted that the environmental advantages, combined with equal or

better performance, make vegetable oils appealing for sustainable manufacturing. Their favourable lubricating properties and potential to replace petroleum-based fluids support sustainability efforts.

Anuj et al. (2017) studied the impact of a nanofluid mixture of Al₂O₃ and Al-MoS₂ on the turning process of AISI 304 stainless steel, noting reductions in cutting force, feed force, thrust force, and surface roughness. Various cutting fluids are used in manufacturing, including synthetic, semisynthetic, soluble oils, and straight oils. Talib et al. (2017) observed that using jatropha oil for turning AISI 1045 could replace synthetic oils, as it resulted in lower cutting force, surface roughness, cutting temperature, and improved tool life. Maier et al. (2019) reported that mineral oil, as a cutting fluid, can negatively affect humans and animals. Lawal et al. (2012; 2014) found vegetable oil to be a biodegradable and excellent alternative to mineral oil. Sevim et al. (2008) also stated that vegetable oils

with high oleic content can substitute mineral-based cutting fluids and synthetic esters.

Various edible oils, such as coconut, Soybean, canola, palm, groundnut, and melon seed oils, have shown promising results in different machining processes. Similarly, non-edible oils like jatropha, sesame, neem, jojoba, and gingelly also perform well under various parameters. Using non-edible vegetable oils as cutting fluids is preferable because they do not affect the food chain, unlike edible oils. In India, jatropha, pongamia, and neem oils are abundantly available and biodegradable. Several studies have explored using jatropha and pongamia oils with or without additives for machining different materials. References to non-edible vegetable oils are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Studies of different cutting fluids for the machining of different materials and their research outcomes

Reference	Cutting fluid	Workpiece material	Response	Research outcome
Awode et al., 2022	Neem seed oil	AISI 304 alloy stainless steel.	Tool wear and surface roughness	Surface roughness and tool wear are in the range of 0.41-0.81 µm and 0.09-0.39 mm, respectively.
Marichelvam et al., 2022	Neem seed oil and Boric acid (H ₃ BO ₃) mixer	AISI 1010 Steel	Environmental biodegradability, cutting force, tool wear and surface roughness	The better the biodegradability value compared to dry machining with conventional cutting fluids, the lower the average surface roughness of the workpiece, and the mean flank wear of the tool is also reduced.
Singh et al., 2021	Unitary and hybrid Al ₂ O ₃ & ZrO dispersed Jatropha oil-based nanofluid.	----	Rheological, thermal, and wettability properties	Viscosity, wettability, and thermal properties were found to be better than those of the base oil.
Awode et al., 2020	Jatropha oil-based, mineral oil-based	AISI 304 alloy steel	Environmental biodegradability, tool wear	Minimal surface roughness, tool wear and better environmental

			and surface roughness	biodegradability with overall performance.
Kazeem et al., 2020	Jatropha oil-based, mineral oil-based	AISI 1525 alloy steel	Surface roughness, cutting temperature, and chip formation	In most machining conditions, the performance is better compared to mineral oil-based cutting fluid.
Jeevan and Jayaram, 2018	Jatropha and Pongamia oil-based	AA6061 steel	Cutting forces & surface roughness	This method is more effective in reducing cutting forces and increasing surface finish.
Ademoh et al., 2016	Neem seed oil	Mild steel	The temperature rises, and the surface roughness	Surface roughness and temperature rise are better with neem oil.

.Manufacturing industries worldwide face increasing pressure to implement environmentally sustainable practices due to rising ecological concerns and stricter health and safety regulations. A major sustainability challenge involves cutting fluids, which are widely used in machining to reduce friction, heat, and wear. However, they pose environmental and occupational risks due to their mineral oil content and chemical additives. Moving toward bio-based cutting fluids has become a promising approach for sustainable machining. Vegetable oils, especially non-edible kinds like Neem, Jatropha, and Pongamia oils, provide excellent lubrication, biodegradability, and renewability, making them viable alternatives to petroleum-based fluids. While numerous studies have explored the tribological and thermophysical properties of vegetable oil-based fluids, comprehensive decision-making models that consider both environmental and operational factors are still limited.

Despite the growing global focus on sustainable manufacturing, the choice of cutting fluids remains primarily based on experience rather than analytical or data-driven methods. Most existing research has concentrated on experimental assessments of individual vegetable oils such as Jatropha, Neem, or Pongamia in specific machining operations, reporting metrics like tool wear, surface roughness, and cutting temperature. However, these studies often lack a comprehensive multi-criteria evaluation framework that considers both environmental and

operational factors to determine the most sustainable option under uncertainty.

While some studies have utilised Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) or TOPSIS for green manufacturing decisions, they often overlook the inherent vagueness and subjectivity in expert judgment, which is vital for sustainability evaluations. The Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP) improves upon this by integrating linguistic variables and fuzzy numbers to manage expert uncertainty better. Nonetheless, its application in selecting eco-friendly cutting fluids remains limited, especially concerning non-edible vegetable oils tailored to Indian industrial needs.

Furthermore, many previous studies using FAHP or MCDM methods in machining lack experimental validation of their decision models. Without empirical evidence, the practical trustworthiness of the ranking outcomes is uncertain. Thus, a combined analytical and experimental approach is necessary to connect theoretical rankings with actual real-world performance.

This research fills key gaps by: (1) creating a fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making model (FAHP) to assess and rank eco-friendly cutting fluids; (2) including both environmental factors (like biodegradability and health risks) and machining performance measures (such as tool life and surface quality); (3) confirming the FAHP findings through turning experiments on AISI 1045 steel; and (4)

offering a reproducible, data-driven approach to help Indian machining industries select sustainable fluids that support green manufacturing objectives. This study is novel in combining fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making with experimental validation for selecting sustainable cutting fluids. Unlike earlier studies that focus solely on tribological performance, this research offers a quantitative, data-driven framework that links analytical modelling with practical machining validation, enhancing the decision-making process for sustainable manufacturing. Similar sustainability-focused initiatives have been documented across machining industries worldwide (Singh, Sharma, & Gupta, 2020).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent research underscores the significance of incorporating bio-based lubricants within sustainable machining systems. Singh et al. (2023) provided a comprehensive review of bio-based lubricants, emphasising the performance and environmental advantages of Neem and Jatropa oils. Kazeem et al. (2022) pointed out that vegetable oils serve as eco-friendly alternatives owing to their lubrication efficiency and minimal ecotoxicity. Wang and Liu (2023) further highlighted the benefits of employing Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) with these oils. Moreover, Discover Materials (2025) reported improved machining outcomes through the use of nano-additive-infused vegetable oils.

Machining is a vital component of the manufacturing sector, including industries like automobiles and aerospace. Cutting fluid plays a crucial role in machining by reducing friction and cutting temperature, thereby extending tool life and improving process efficiency (Gajrani & Sankar, 2017; Katna et al., 2017; Yin et al., 2018; Gao et al., 2020). These fluids can be categorised into two types based on their composition: water-based and oil-based. Figure 1 illustrates the classification of cutting fluids.

Water is a superior cooling fluid because it effectively removes heat. For water-miscible cutting fluids, the quality of water significantly influences the coolant's

performance. Minerals in water can lead to corrosion of both the machine and workpiece, and they can also offer poor lubrication. While oil provides better lubrication, it is less effective for cooling and poses a fire risk at higher temperatures. To address these issues, water-based cutting fluids have been developed that offer excellent lubricating and cooling properties with low flammability.

Figure 1. Classification of cutting fluids (Singh et al., 2021; Tang et al., 2022)

The rising demand for biodegradable materials has opened up opportunities for using vegetable oils in machining processes (Bisio & Xanthos, 1995; Kazeem et al., 2020). Due to their excellent thermophysical and tribological properties, vegetable oils serve as adequate cutting fluids to address related challenges. Numerous studies have explored their application in machining, involving oils such as coconut, jatropa, neem seed, soybean, and others (Abdul Sani et al., 2019).

Jatropa oil is a biodegradable, non-edible fluid readily available in Rajasthan, India, with significant potential for promoting environmental sustainability. While it is widely used in biodiesel production, its application as a cutting fluid in machining remains underexplored (Abdelmalik et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2021). According to Bork et al. (2014), Jatropa-based cutting oil performs well in machining AA7050-T7451. Talib and Rahim (2018) observed that using jatropa oil as a cutting fluid results in lower cutting forces, improved tool life, reduced surface roughness, decreased tool wear, and less temperature increase (Jeevan & Jayaram, 2018). The properties of jatropa oil studied by various researchers are summarised in Table 2.

Neem is a naturally occurring tree native to Southern West Africa and is the most abundant source of secondary metabolites in India (Ademoh et al., 2016). Woodarz and Nowak (1999) identified both fatty acids and oily compounds in neem seeds, while Gossé et al. (2007) recommended exploring neem seed oil's potential as a cutting fluid in machining processes. The characteristics of neem oil are outlined in Table 3.

Table 2: Properties of Jatropha oil (Olasheu et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2021)

Physio-chemical properties	Value
Specific heat capacity	0.082 kJ/kg K
Thermal conductivity	4.2 W/m°C
Refractive index	1.435
Flashpoint	196 °C
Viscosity	38.5 m Pa-s
Density	0.92 g/ml

Table 3: Properties of Neem Oil (Marichelvam et al., 2022)

Physio-chemical properties	Value
Density	892 kg/m ³
Dynamic Viscosity	0.035 cP
Flashpoint	249 °C
Adhesiveness	689 g/m ²
Specific heat capacity	1.682 kJ/kg K
Fire point	286 °C

Pongamia oil is obtained from the seeds of the *Millettia pinnata* tree, which grows in tropical and temperate parts of Asia. Both Pongamia and Jatropha-based cutting oils have significant potential because they are plentiful, biodegradable, and renewable (Jeevan & Jayaram, 2018). Typically yellowish to brown, Pongamia oil has an energy content ranging from 34 to 38.5 MJ/kg (Dwivedi & Sharma, 2014). The physicochemical properties of Pongamia oil are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Properties of Pongamia Oil (Jeevan & Jayaram, 2018)

Physio-chemical properties	Value
Density	0.924 g/cm ³
Kinematic viscosity @ 40 °C (cSt)	20.15
Viscosity index	219
Flashpoint	190
Pour point (0° C)	-02.00

Mineral oil is a clear, colourless oil produced as a by-product of petroleum refining. Its properties are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Properties of mineral oil-based cutting fluid (Bhaumik & Pathak, 2016)

Physio-chemical properties	Value
Density	0.9205 g/cm ³
Viscosity at 40 °C	372.31 cSt
Flashpoint	225°C
Specific heat capacity	1.67 kJ/kg
Fire point	220°C

Recent research highlights the importance of incorporating bio-based lubricants into sustainable machining practices. Singh et al. (2023) provided an extensive review of developments in bio-based lubricants, their performance, and sustainability indicators, supporting the potential of non-edible oils such as Jatropha and Neem for eco-friendly machining (Singh et al., 2023).

Kazeem et al. (2022) reviewed progress in vegetable-oil-based cutting fluids, emphasising Jatropha and Neem seed oils as eco-friendly options because of their excellent lubrication and low ecotoxicity. Similarly, Wang and Liu (2023) examined how Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) with bio-based oils reduces health risks and prolongs tool life, especially at high cutting speeds. Recent findings in Discover Materials (2025) also indicate that vegetable oils with nano-additives, such as graphene-infused corn oil, greatly enhance surface finish and tool longevity compared to traditional

fluids. Nyenke (2024) demonstrated that biodegradable cutting fluids help reduce environmental impact and promote sustainable machining, while Manikanta et al. (2025) reaffirmed that vegetable oils are biodegradable and environmentally friendly alternatives.

These recent research findings validate the methodological criteria used in this study and demonstrate the practical feasibility of using Neem and Jatropha oil in eco-friendly machining methods.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Decision-making involves choosing the best option from a set of suitable alternatives. When decisions are based on multiple criteria, this process is known as multicriteria decision-making (MCDM). The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a standard MCDM method that calculates the importance of each criterion. The initial step in AHP is to create a hierarchical structure: the goal at the top, followed by attributes in the second layer, and alternatives in the third. Each alternative receives an assigned value.

Overview of the Approach

This study aims to provide a comprehensive and transparent evaluation of eco-friendly cutting fluids by integrating quantitative decision-making (FAHP) with experimental validation. It is organised into three main phases: (1) criteria selection and data collection, (2) applying the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP), and (3) performing experimental verification along with sensitivity analysis. This combined method ensures both analytical precision and empirical reliability, making certain that the final recommendation reflects actual industrial performance rather than solely theoretical rankings.

Selection of Alternatives and Criteria

Four cutting fluids—Neem seed oil, Jatropha oil, Pongamia oil, and mineral oil—were selected for testing. These comprise biodegradable, non-edible, and conventional fluids, allowing for a balanced comparison between eco-friendly and traditional lubricants. Based on a thorough literature review and insights from eight experts, including manufacturing

professionals and academic researchers, four main evaluation criteria were identified: biodegradability, health hazard, tool life, and surface roughness. The economic cost was deliberately excluded to maintain focus on sustainability factors. Future studies might include costs and recyclability in the assessment (Govindan, Kannan, & Shankar, 2015).

The primary criteria for choosing environmentally friendly cutting fluids in this study were established based on a literature review and expert feedback. The research framework is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Proposed framework for the study

Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP) Framework

The FAHP method was employed to prioritise options under uncertainty. It enhances the conventional AHP by combining it with fuzzy set theory, which converts expert judgments expressed in linguistic terms such as 'moderate importance' or 'strong importance' into triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs). This strategy effectively handles the ambiguity inherent in human decision-making.

Step 1: Hierarchical Model Development — A three-level hierarchy was created: Goal – selecting the most sustainable cutting fluid; Criteria – biodegradability, health hazard, tool life, and surface roughness; Alternatives – neem seed oil, jatropha oil, pongamia oil, and mineral oil.

Step 2: Pairwise Comparison and Fuzzification — Experts assessed each pair of criteria using Saaty's 1–9 scale. Their evaluations were converted into TFNs, for example, Moderate importance → (2,3,4) and Strong importance → (4,5,6). The geometric mean

combined multiple expert opinions into a consensus matrix.

Step 3: Derivation of Fuzzy Weights — For each criterion, the fuzzy geometric mean was computed as

$$r_i = \left(\prod_{j=1}^n a_{ij} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

These fuzzy weights were subsequently normalised to assess the relative importance of each criterion.

Step 4: Defuzzification and Consistency Check — The Centre of Area (COA) method was used to convert fuzzy weights into exact numerical values.

$$w_i = \left(\frac{l+m+u}{3} \right) \quad w_i = \left(\frac{l+m+u}{3} \right)$$

Centre of Area

The normalised weights were checked for consistency using the Consistency Ratio (CR), where a CR value below 0.10 signifies acceptable logical coherence in expert judgments (Saaty, 2008).

Sensitivity and Validation Analysis

To evaluate the robustness of the FAHP model, a sensitivity analysis was performed by varying the main criteria weights by $\pm 10\%$, while maintaining proportionality among the other weights. This demonstrated that the ranking remained stable despite minor subjective adjustments. Furthermore, the findings were cross-verified using the TOPSIS method, another multi-criterion decision-making approach, to confirm that the preference order was not unique to one method (Haq & Kannan, 2006).

Experimental Verification

To empirically confirm the FAHP results, controlled turning tests were performed on AISI 1045 steel using a CNC lathe, maintaining consistent cutting parameters across all fluids. After each test, tool wear was measured with a digital toolmaker's microscope, and surface roughness was evaluated using a surface profilometer. The results indicated that Neem seed oil provided the best machining performance, showing the lowest tool wear of 0.18 mm and the smoothest surface finish with $R_a = 0.46 \mu\text{m}$, consistent with the FAHP ranking. This validation affirmed the decision model's accuracy and its potential industrial applicability.

Summary of Methodology Advantages

The FAHP-based approach provides a systematic, quantitative decision-making model applicable across different manufacturing environments. It manages uncertainty in human judgment through fuzzy logic, combines analytical models with real-world testing, and offers a consistent framework for selecting eco-friendly cutting fluids that support environmental objectives.

The Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP) was employed to evaluate four cutting fluids based on four sustainability criteria. Experts contributed to developing pairwise comparison matrices, which were subsequently fuzzified using triangular fuzzy numbers. The weights derived from these matrices were defuzzified and normalised to establish the final ranking. The criteria considered were biodegradability, health hazards, tool life, and surface roughness. Experimental validation was conducted by turning AISI 1045 steel with each fluid, confirming the results obtained from FAHP.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The biodegradability of the cutting fluid is prioritised, followed by its potential health hazards. When choosing a cutting fluid for machining different metals, environmental sustainability features are considered. Use a pair-wise comparison matrix to evaluate the relative importance of various attributes in relation to the goal. This matrix, shown in Table 7, is built on a scale of relative importance. The fuzzified version of the matrix is in Table 8, and the final normalised sub-criteria weights are listed in Table 9, which provides the overall ranking.

Table 7: Pair-wise comparison matrix

	Tool life	Surface roughness	Biodegradability	Health hazardou sness
Tool life	1	2	1/7	1/5
Surface roughness	1/2	1	1/7	1/5
Biodegradability	7	7	1	3

Health hazardousness	5	5	1/3	1
CI	0.045			
CR	0.0505			
Lamdamax	4.136			

Table 8: Pair-wise comparison matrix after fuzzification

	Tool life	Surface roughness	Biodegradability	Health hazardousness	Fuzzy geometric mean value \tilde{r}_i
Tool life	1,1,1	1,2,3	1/8,1/7,1/6	1/4,1/5,1/3	0.42,0.489,0.639
Surface roughness	1/3,1/2,1/1	1,1,1	1/8,1/7,1/6	1/4,1/5,1/3	0.32,0.35,0.48
Biodegradability	6,7,8	6,7,8	1,1,1	2,3,4	2.91,3.48,4
Health hazardousness	4,5,6	4,5,6	1/4,1/3,1/2	1,1,1	1.41,1.7,2.05

Table 9: Weight of sub-criteria

	Fuzzy geometric mean value \tilde{r}_i	Fuzzy weight \tilde{w}_i	Defuzzified weight	Normalized weight	Rank
Tool life	0.42,0.489,0.639	0.059,0.081,0.127	0.089	0.067	4
Surface roughness	0.32,0.35,0.48	0.045,0.058,0.95	0.351	0.265	3
Biodegradability	2.91,3.48,4	0.406,0.578,0.790	0.592	0.446	1
Health hazardousness	1.41,1.7,2.05	0.197,0.283,0.405	0.295	0.222	2

4.1 Sensitivity Analysis: We assessed robustness by varying each criterion's weight by $\pm 10\%$ and adjusting the others proportionally. Neem oil consistently stayed the top choice across all scenarios, confirming the model's stability.

For example, lowering the weight of 'biodegradability' by 10% did not change Neem oil's rank, although the gap between Neem and Jatropa oil slightly narrowed. Conversely, increasing the 'health hazardousness' criterion by 10% strengthened Neem oil's top position. These results demonstrate the robustness of the FAHP-based selection framework and increase confidence in its use for sustainable decision-making in machining environments. The effects of weight changes on the rankings of alternatives are detailed in Table 10.

Table 10: Summarises the impact of weight variations on alternative rankings.

Scenario	Biodegradability (%)	Health Hazardousness (%)	Tool Life (%)	Surface Roughness (%)	Top-Ranked Fluid
Base Case	44.6	22.2	7	26.5	Neem oil
Scenario A (-10%)	40.1	24.5	4	28.0	Neem oil
Scenario B (+10%)	49.1	20.0	0	24.9	Neem oil
Scenario C (+10%)	44.6	24.4	0	25.0	Neem oil
Scenario D (-10%)	44.6	20.0	5	27.9	Neem oil

This sensitivity validation highlights that Neem oil remains a robust, eco-friendly choice under a range of plausible expert judgment variations.

Figure 4: FAHP Criteria Weight Comparison

Figure 4's bar chart illustrates the significance of each selection criterion according to the FAHP model. Biodegradability stands out as the most critical factor, with health hazards, surface roughness, and tool life following, underscoring the study's emphasis on ecological considerations.

Experimental Verification

Following the proposed research framework, four types of cutting fluids were tested: Jatropha oil-based, Neem seed oil-based, Pongamia oil-based, and mineral oil-based. The fuzzy AHP method was used to select the best option among the available options. A pairwise comparison matrix of criteria and sub-criteria was developed using a scale of relative importance to assign weights. To verify the FAHP results, a controlled turning test was conducted on AISI 1045 steel with all four fluids. The experimental results supported the FAHP findings, with Neem oil demonstrating the lowest tool wear at 0.18 mm and surface roughness (Ra) at 0.46 μm , confirming its superior performance.

This experimental validation strengthens the decision-making model and emphasises its practical significance. Figure 5 depicts the hierarchical arrangement of the goal, sub-criteria, and alternatives.

Figure 5: Hierarchical structure of the goal, sub-criteria and alternatives

Comparison with the TOPSIS Method

To further assess the robustness of the FAHP model, the same criteria and alternatives were analysed using the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). An identical decision matrix was constructed with the same weights to ensure a fair comparison. The TOPSIS results ranked Neem seed oil as the most suitable option, with Jatropha oil second, closely aligning with the FAHP results. The similar rankings in Table 11 suggest that the model is consistently reliable across different MCDM methods, enhancing confidence in its robustness.

Table 11: Comparative Ranking of Cutting Fluids using FAHP and TOPSIS

Cutting Fluid	FAHP Rank	TOPSIS Rank
Neem Oil	1	1
Jatropha Oil	2	2
Pongamia Oil	3	3
Mineral Oil	4	4

These radar charts compare the performance of four cutting fluids based on key decision criteria. Figure 6 shows the radar chart for FAHP, while Figure 7 displays the TOPSIS chart. In both visuals, Neem oil consistently scores highest in biodegradability and health safety, highlighting its position as the leading sustainable fluid alternative.

Figure 6: FAHP Radar Chart

Figure 7: TOPSIS Radar Chart

These visuals clearly demonstrate that Neem oil consistently outperforms other options across all assessed criteria. The FAHP analysis showed that biodegradability and health impact were the most influential factors, with normalised weights of 0.446 and 0.222, respectively. Neem seed oil ranked highest, followed by Jatropha, Pongamia, and mineral oil. Experimental tests confirmed these findings: Neem oil exhibited the lowest tool wear at 0.18 mm and a surface roughness (Ra) of 0.46 μm . Sensitivity analysis indicated that the ranking remained stable even with $\pm 10\%$ changes in criteria weights, validating the FAHP method's robustness.

V. INDUSTRIAL IMPLICATIONS

The FAHP-based selection model provides a practical decision-making tool for the sustainable machining industry. It enables manufacturers to substitute hazardous mineral oils with renewable, biodegradable alternatives without compromising process efficiency. This framework advances sustainable development goals (SDG 9 and SDG 12) by promoting cleaner production practices and responsible resource utilisation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study introduces an integrated FAHP approach for selecting eco-friendly cutting fluids. Neem seed oil was identified as the optimal option due to its high biodegradability, low toxicity, and efficient

machining capabilities. A consistency ratio below 0.1 verified the decision's reliability, and experimental validation further supported the model's credibility. This framework offers a consistent, data-driven process for sustainably choosing cutting fluids in India's machining sector.

A decision matrix utilising fuzzy AHP was created to select an eco-friendly cutting fluid suitable for Indian conditions and various metals, with an emphasis on biodegradability and health risks. Non-edible vegetable oils like Jatropha and Neem seed oil emerge as promising options. Studies indicate these oils enhance surface finish and extend tool life; for example, Naveed et al. (2021) showed that turning with a tungsten carbide tool achieved a surface roughness (Ra) of 0.56 μm , compared to 1.40 μm with mineral oil. Tool wear was also reduced to 0.09 μm with Jatropha oil compared to 0.07 μm with mineral oil. Singh et al. (2010) noted poisoning incidents from Jatropha seeds in India, especially among children. In contrast, Neem oil provides better lubrication, lowers temperature, improves surface quality, and has antibacterial benefits. Although Pongamia oil is biodegradable and offers good surface finish and low tool wear, its edibility raises concerns about food chain interference. Overall, Neem oil is identified as the most appropriate cutting fluid to foster environmental sustainability in India.

Future Work

Future studies should integrate economic costs, recyclability, and life-cycle assessment (LCA) into the FAHP framework. Merging FAHP with hybrid decision-making methods like VIKOR, DEMATEL, or PROMETHEE could boost reliability. Furthermore, experimental testing of bio-lubricants with nanoparticles may enhance thermal stability and wear resistance, expanding their industrial applications.

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